

A Practical Guide to Spectral Fault Receptive Fields: Parameterization and Usage in the SFRFs MATLAB Toolbox

(Applicable to SFRFs MATLAB Toolbox versions 1.1.x)

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Abstract

Purpose. This guide introduces the parameterization and practical use of Spectral Fault Receptive Fields (SFRFs) within the MATLAB toolbox (version 1.1.x), with emphasis on their role as a structured framework for condition indicator (CI) construction.

Approach. This guide demonstrates the SFRFs MATLAB toolbox, covering the workflow from installation to the definition of customized receptive field responses. It compares SFRF-based responses with standard condition indicators and illustrates how the new parameterizations enable the injection of custom Receptive Field Response Functions (RFRFs), allowing classical spectral descriptors to be embedded within the harmonic lattices induced by characteristic fault frequencies. The guide follows a concept-driven traversal of the design space and demonstrates its usage on run-to-failure data from the XJTU-SY open dataset.

Key insights. Receptive Field Response Functions (RFRFs) provide sufficient flexibility to construct perceptual channels with varying sensitivity to degradation phenomena. SFRF-based condition indicators (CIs) do not replace standard indicators; instead, they organize them into controllable perceptual channels. Effective characterization benefits from a multi-channel perspective, reflecting trade-offs between sensitivity, smoothness, and interpretability.

Implementation. The toolbox supports flexible experimentation through behavior injection, and practical deployment through logging and parallelization, enabling integration into PHM workflows.

Contribution. The SFRF framework provides a structured mechanism for selectively harnessing spectral information through parameterized receptive fields, supporting fault-oriented analysis of degradation in rotating machinery.

Keywords: Health Perception · Condition Monitoring · Spectral Fault Receptive Fields (SFRFs) Receptive Fields Response Functions (RFRFs) · Contrast Mappings · MATLAB Toolbox

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1 How to Use This Guide

The SFRFs MATLAB toolbox includes extensive documentation in the form of interactive **Live Scripts** and their corresponding **HTML exports**, which provide artifact-level descriptions of the implemented components and workflows.

This guide does not attempt to replicate that material. Instead, it offers a structured, concept-driven traversal of the SFRF design space, with emphasis on parameterization choices, usage patterns, and the interpretation of resulting condition indicators.

It is intended as an entry point for understanding how the components of the toolbox can be composed to construct meaningful perceptual channels for condition monitoring and prognosis.

Note. We recommend executing the sections of this notebook sequentially.

2 Toolbox Availability

The SFRFs MATLAB toolbox is publicly available and distributed through the following channels.

```
test_sfrfs
```

- The canonical, versioned release is hosted on Zenodo [2], providing a stable and citable archive of the toolbox: <https://zenodo.org/records/18444293>.

- The source code and ongoing development are available on GitHub: <https://github.com/stanmoon/matlab-sfrfs>, caption=Run test suite.
- A packaged version is also available via the MATLAB File Exchange under the name *Spectral Fault Receptive Fields*, enabling direct installation and integration within the MATLAB environment: <https://www.mathworks.com/matlabcentral/fileexchange/182798-spectral-fault-receptive-fields>.

3 Toolbox Installation and Verification

The SFRFs MATLAB toolbox can be installed through any of the distribution channels listed above. For most users, the recommended option is the packaged release available via the MATLAB File Exchange, which integrates the toolbox directly into the MATLAB environment (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Toolbox installation via Add-On Manager.

Alternatively, the toolbox can be obtained from Zenodo or GitHub and added to the MATLAB path manually. After installation, it is recommended to verify that the toolbox is correctly configured and accessible. A minimal verification can be performed by running the test suite provided with the toolbox.

```

1 test_sfrfs

Running all SFRFs tests, this may take a few seconds...

[output truncated]

-----
Totals:
Passed   : 177
Failed   : 0
Incomplete : 0
Time     : 93.292 seconds testing time

```

Successful execution of the test suite, with all tests passing, confirms that the toolbox is correctly installed and operational. At this point, the user can proceed with the examples developed in this guide. If the verification step does not complete successfully, any installation or configuration issues should be resolved before continuing, as subsequent sections assume a correctly functioning environment.

4 Preparing the XJTU-SY Demonstration Dataset

This section prepares the [XJTU-SY](#) [3] run-to-failure bearing dataset for the examples developed in this guide. It provides a compact, self-contained setup path so that the demonstration can be reproduced without navigating other notebooks. The procedure focuses on the minimal steps required to obtain a `fileEnsembleDatastore` object for SFRF parameterization and analysis. Full onboarding material and artifact-level documentation are available in the toolbox documentation and the Getting Started guide.

The demonstration uses the XJTU-SY run-to-failure dataset, which contains vibration signals collected under three operating conditions and multiple bearing instances. The dataset is expected to be organized in a root directory containing subfolders for each operating condition and bearing.

The setup is intentionally streamlined and consists of two stages.

1. The first stage corresponds to one-time preparation, including dataset acquisition, extraction, and ensemble construction.
2. The second stage corresponds to guide initialization, ensuring that the processed data are available and properly registered for use in subsequent examples.

The one-time preparation stage constructs or recovers an ensemble representation of the dataset. If an existing ensemble is available, it is reused directly. Otherwise, the raw vibration signals are processed and assembled into an ensemble datastore.

The guide initialization stage ensures that the spectral representations required for SFRF computation are available. If necessary, the Fourier transform is computed and appended as additional columns. The datastore is then configured so that the spectral columns are accessible to the SFRF processing pipeline.

At the end of this procedure, the user obtains a ready-to-use handle to the prepared ensemble. This handle is used throughout the guide to construct and evaluate SFRF parameterizations.

4.1 Obtaining the Dataset

Download the XJTU-SY bearing dataset from an [official repository](#) and extract it to a local folder. The download process via Google Drive is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Download process for the XJTU-SY dataset via Google Drive.

4.2 Extraction of Dataset Files

Extracting the dataset files is a two-step process. After download, several zip files are created, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Zip files of the XJTU-SY dataset after download.

In Linux, the files can be extracted by executing the following command from the directory where the zip files are located.

```
1 find . -maxdepth 1 -type f -name "*.zip" -exec unzip {} \;
```

This command creates the Data folder, into which the .rar archive parts are extracted (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Multipart archive in .rar format.

To extract the dataset files, execute the following command, providing the first part of the multipart archive.

```
1 unrar x ./Data/XJTU-SY_Bearing_Datasets.part01.rar .
```

The extracted root folder will be selected during the ensemble creation step.

4.3 Creating Datastore Folder

Once the dataset files have been extracted, a target folder for the datastore files (MATLAB files) must be created.

Figure 6: Dialog for selecting the root folder containing the XJTU-SY dataset files.

Figure 7: Dialog for selecting the target folder for the datastore, corresponding to the Datastore folder.

Figure 8: Datastore MATLAB files for the XJTU-SY dataset.

4.5.1 Obtain Ensemble Handle

First, obtain a handle to the existing ensemble by selecting its folder.

```
1 % Obtain a handle to an existing ensemble by selecting its folder via GUI
2 % This creates a configured fileEnsembleDatastore without loading any data
3 ensemble = data.getXJTUSYEnsemble();
```

4.5.2 Register Ensemble

The ensemble is then registered in the datastore registry under the name "XJTU-SY".

This operation does not load the data, but creates a configured datastore for subsequent processing.

```
1 % Register XJTU-SY dataset in the registry
2 EnsembleDatastoreRegistry.addEnsemble( ...
3     name = "XJTU-SY", ...
4     datastore = ensemble);
```

4.5.3 Retrieving Handle to Ensemble

After registration, the ensemble can be retrieved from the registry using its name.

```
1 % Recover the registered datastore
2 ds = EnsembleDatastoreRegistry.getEnsemble("XJTU-SY");
3 disp(ds);
```

```
fileEnsembleDatastore with properties:
```

```
    ReadFcn: @readMember
    WriteToMemberFcn: @writeMember
    DataVariables: [2x1 string]
    IndependentVariables: [2x1 string]
    ConditionVariables: [3x1 string]
    SelectedVariables: [7x1 string]
    ReadSize: 1
    NumMembers: 15
    LastMemberRead: [0x0 string]
    Files: [15x1 string]
```

5 Temporal Domain - Vibration Signals

5.1 Temporal Domain Specification

The dataset consists of vibration signals acquired from rolling element bearings operating under different conditions.

- Each signal represents acceleration measurements recorded along fixed sensor orientations.
- These temporal signals capture the dynamic response of the system, including periodic components associated with rotation and fault-induced modulations.
- The sampling frequency and acquisition parameters define the temporal resolution and duration of each observation.
- These quantities determine the corresponding frequency resolution after transformation to the spectral domain.

To specify the minimal signal parameters, a snapshot descriptor is defined as follows.

```

1 % Creates the descriptor for signal snapshots of XJTU-SY dataset
2 sp = ParametersSnapshot(...)
3     'samplingFrequency', 25600, ...
4     'duration', 1.28, ...
5     'stride', 60)

```

```

sp =
ParametersSnapshot with properties:

    samplingFrequency: 25600
           duration: 1.2800
                stride: 60

```

This specification implies that accelerometer signals are recorded once per minute, with 25,600 samples acquired per second over a duration of 1.28 s for each snapshot.

5.2 Access to Raw Vibration Signals

Raw temporal signals can be accessed by retrieving a handle to the XJTU-SY datastore and iterating over its members. Each member corresponds to the vibration data of a single bearing. Each snapshot is associated with an index that relates to its relative location in time.

```

1 % Retrieve datastore from the registry
2 ds = EnsembleDatastoreRegistry.getEnsemble("XJTU-SY");
3
4 % Reset datastore access
5 reset(ds);
6
7 % Read first member (single bearing instance)
8 firstMember = read(ds);
9
10 % Display first snapshots (rows) of the member
11 head(firstMember);

```

Label	SnapshotIndex	HorizontalAcceleration	VerticalAcceleration	Speed	Load	Lifetime
"Bearing1_1"	1	32768x1 double	32768x1 double	35	12	123
"Bearing1_1"	2	32768x1 double	32768x1 double	35	12	123
"Bearing1_1"	3	32768x1 double	32768x1 double	35	12	123
"Bearing1_1"	4	32768x1 double	32768x1 double	35	12	123
"Bearing1_1"	5	32768x1 double	32768x1 double	35	12	123
"Bearing1_1"	6	32768x1 double	32768x1 double	35	12	123
"Bearing1_1"	7	32768x1 double	32768x1 double	35	12	123
"Bearing1_1"	8	32768x1 double	32768x1 double	35	12	123

Temporal signals are provided in the `HorizontalAcceleration` and `VerticalAcceleration` fields. A signal can be plotted as follows:

```

1 plot(sp.getTimeAxis(), firstMember.HorizontalAcceleration{1});
2 xlabel('Time (s)'); ylabel('Acceleration (g)');
3 title('Horizontal acceleration signal')
4 axis tight

```


These signals constitute the raw input from which snapshot-wise responses are computed.

6 Working in the Spectral Domain

The analysis developed in this guide is carried out in the spectral domain. Rather than operating on raw temporal signals, the data are transformed into frequency representations that expose the harmonic structure of the underlying physical processes. This enables the construction of perceptual channels that selectively emphasize different aspects of bearing degradation.

6.1 Computation of Spectra of Vibration Signals

The transformation to the spectral domain is performed by computing the Fourier transform of the temporal signals. The toolbox provides the classes `FFTEnsembleProcessor` and `SFRFsEnsembleBroker` to apply this transformation across the ensemble and interface with the `fileEnsembleDatastore`. The following computation may take several minutes.

```

1  % Temporal signal columns
2  temporalSnapshotColumns = { ...
3      'HorizontalAcceleration', ...
4      'VerticalAcceleration'};
5
6  % Retrieve ensemble
7  ensemble = EnsembleDatastoreRegistry.getEnsemble("XJTU-SY");
8
9  % Create ensemble broker
10 broker = SFRFsEnsembleBroker( ...
11     EnsembleObject = ensemble, ...
12     GetFilesFunction = @(obj) obj.Files, ...
13     TemporalSnapshotColumns = temporalSnapshotColumns);
14
15 % Create FFT processor
16 % Adjust the number of workers according to system capabilities
17 processor = FFTEnsembleProcessor( ...
18     numWorkers = 6, ...

```

```

19     ensemble = broker);
20 % Execute FFT computation (parallel)
21 processor.process();

```

```

Starting parallel pool (parpool) using the 'Processes' profile ...
Connected to parallel pool with 6 workers.

```

6.2 Updating the Registry

The resulting spectral representations are stored as additional columns in the ensemble and serve as the basis for subsequent SFRF construction. These columns are not yet visible, so the ensemble must be reconfigured to include them. The following code obtains their names.

```

1 % Spectral column names
2 FFTCols = string( ...
3     cellfun(@(c) broker.mapToSpectralColumn(c), ...
4     temporalSnapshotColumns, ...
5     'UniformOutput', false)).';
6
7 disp(FFTCols);

```

```

"HorizontalAcceleration_FFT"
"VerticalAcceleration_FFT"

```

The following cell updates the registry with the new data variables and selects the FFT columns.

```

1 % Retrieve datastore
2 ds = EnsembleDatastoreRegistry.getEnsemble("XJTU-SY");
3
4 % Reconfigure ensemble with spectral columns
5 ds = EnsembleDatastoreRegistry.reconfigureEnsemble( ...
6     name = "XJTU-SY", ...
7     DataVariables = ...
8         unique([ds.DataVariables(:); FFTCols(:)], "stable"), ...
9     SelectedVariables = ...
10        unique([ds.SelectedVariables(:); FFTCols(:)], "stable"));
11
12 disp(ds);

```

```

fileEnsembleDatastore with properties:

```

```

    ReadFcn: @readMember
    WriteToMemberFcn: @writeMember
    DataVariables: [4x1 string]
    IndependentVariables: [2x1 string]
    ConditionVariables: [3x1 string]
    SelectedVariables: [9x1 string]
    ReadSize: 1
    NumMembers: 15
    LastMemberRead: [0x0 string]
    Files: [15x1 string]

```

6.3 Access to Spectra and Visualization

Package viz provides basic visualization helpers.

```

1 % Retrieve datastore
2 ds = EnsembleDatastoreRegistry.getEnsemble("XJTU-SY");
3
4 % Reset datastore

```

```

5 reset(ds);
6
7 % Read first member
8 firstMember = read(ds);
9
10 % Visualize spectra
11 v = viz.RunToFailureSpectraViewer( ...
12     memberTable = firstMember, ...
13     snapshotParameters = sp);
14
15 v.renderRunToFailure( ...
16     spectralColumn = FFTCols(1), ...
17     titleText = "Amplitude spectra");

```


Particular frequency ranges can be examined in detail. The following cell focuses on the band 85 Hz to 250 Hz.

```

1 % Visualize spectra
2 v = viz.RunToFailureSpectraViewer( ...
3     memberTable = firstMember, ...
4     snapshotParameters = sp);
5
6 v.renderRunToFailure( ...
7     spectralColumn = FFTCols(1), ...
8     freqRange = [85 250], ...
9     titleText = "Amplitude spectra (horizontal, 85--250 Hz)");

```


Each temporal snapshot is transformed into a spectral representation from which a scalar response is computed using SFRFs. The sequence of responses across snapshots defines a trend that reflects the evolution of the system over time. In this guide, condition indicators are understood as trends derived from snapshot-wise responses, enabling a consistent interpretation of degradation behavior.

7 Fault Frequency Bands

The SFRFs toolbox focuses on characteristic frequencies associated with healthy and faulty behavior of rotating systems. In the XJTU-SY dataset, bearing defects generate impulsive excitations whose repetition rates depend on bearing geometry and operating conditions.

7.1 Bearing parameters

Bearing parameters can be specified by instantiating the `ParametersRollingBearings` object, as illustrated in the following cell.

```

1 % Bearing geometry parameters
2 bp = ParametersRollingBearings( ...
3     numRollingElements = 8, ...
4     ballDiameter = 7.92, ...
5     pitchDiameter = 34.55, ...
6     contactAngle = 0);
7
8 disp(bp);

```

ParametersRollingBearings with properties:

```

numRollingElements: 8
ballDiameter: 7.9200
pitchDiameter: 34.5500
contactAngle: 0

```

7.2 Operating conditions

Operating conditions are essential for frequency characterization and interpretation of degradation trends. In the toolbox, they refer to system speed and load.

```

1 % Operating conditions
2 speed = [35; 37.5; 40];
3 load = [12; 11; 10];
4
5 oc = OperatingConditions(speed, load);
6
7 disp(oc.conditionsTable);

```

Speed	Load
35	12
37.5	11
40	10

7.3 Frequency Masks

Admissible spectral masks are functions defined over the positive frequency domain that encode explicit epistemic expectations by restricting computation to task-relevant harmonic families. In the SFRFs toolbox, masks are defined over a frequency grid and associated with a band $[f_{min}, f_{max}]$ centered on a characteristic frequency. They act as gain functions that weight spectral components according to their relevance. Version 1.1.x recommends super-Gaussian masks, which generalize the Gaussian profiles introduced in [1] via a shape parameter controlling the transition from sharply peaked ($\beta < 2$) to near-uniform (box-like, $\beta \gg 2$) weighting. A minimal example is provided below; Gaussian profiles are also supported.

```

1 % Frequency axis
2 f = sp.getFrequencyDomain();
3
4 % Frequency band
5 band = [85 250];
6
7 % Super-Gaussian scale parameter
8 alpha = (band(2) - band(1)) / 2;
9
10 % Shape parameters
11 betas = [0.8, 1, 2, 32];
12
13 figure;
14 hold on;
15
16 for b = betas
17     % Mask parameters
18     maskParams = SuperGaussianMaskParameters( ...
19         alpha = alpha, ...
20         beta = b);
21
22     % Evaluate mask
23     G = FrequencyMask.evaluate(f, band, maskParams);
24
25     plot(f, G, 'DisplayName', "\beta = " + b);
26 end
27
28 hold off;
29
30 grid on;
31 xlabel('Frequency (Hz)'); ylabel('Gain');
32 title('Super-Gaussian masks');

```

```

33 legend('Location', 'south');
34 xlim(band);

```


8 SFRFs Parameters

`SFRFsParameters` defines the parameterization of Spectral Fault Receptive Fields (SFRFs), including harmonic structure, sideband structure, and center-surround mask configuration. A minimal example using Gaussian masks for both center and surround is given below. Parameters can be specified independently for each fault type; here a common configuration is used.

```

1  % Shared SFRF parameters (all fault types)
2  % Gaussian masks for center and surround
3  sharedParams = ...
4      SFRFsParameters.buildSFRFsParameters( ...
5      'order', 0, ...
6      'numSidebands', 2, ...
7      'numHarmonics', 10, ...
8      'centerMask', ...
9          GaussianMaskParameters( ...
10         'bandwidth', 4, ...
11         'sigmaRule', 1.0253), ...
12      'surroundMask', ...
13         GaussianMaskParameters( ...
14         'bandwidth', 12, ...
15         'sigmaRule', 0.8905), ...
16      'inhibitionFactor', 0.8647);
17
18 % Supports shared or fault-specific parameterizations
19 sfrfsParams = SFRFsParametersRollingBearings( ...
20     SameForAllFaultTypes = sharedParams);
21
22 disp(sfrfsParams);

```

```
SFRFsParametersRollingBearings with properties:
```

```

    outerRace: [1x1 struct]
    innerRace: [1x1 struct]

```

```

        ball: [1x1 struct]
        cage: [1x1 struct]
OUTER_RACE_FAULT_TYPE_NAME: 'outerRace'
INNER_RACE_FAULT_TYPE_NAME: 'innerRace'
BALL_FAULT_TYPE_NAME: 'ball'
CAGE_FAULT_TYPE_NAME: 'cage'
        faultTypes: 'outerRace' 'innerRace' 'ball' 'cage'
        ORDER_PARAM_NAME: 'order'
        NUM_SIDE BANDS_PARAM_NAME: 'numSidebands'
        NUM_HARMONICS_PARAM_NAME: 'numHarmonics'
        CENTER_MASK_PARAM_NAME: 'centerMask'
        SURROUND_MASK_PARAM_NAME: 'surroundMask'
INHIBITION_FACTOR_PARAM_NAME: 'inhibitionFactor'
        SIGMA_CENTER_PARAM_NAME: 'sigmaCenter'
        SIGMA_SURROUND_PARAM_NAME: 'sigmaSurround'
        sfrfFields: 'order' 'numSidebands' 'numHarmonics' 'sigmaCenter' 'sigmaSurround' 'inhibitionFactor'
        sfrfFieldsForMasks: 'order' 'numSidebands' 'numHarmonics' 'centerMask' 'surroundMask' 'inhibitionFactor'

```

9 Bearing Frequency Bands

Characteristic frequency bands associated with rolling-element bearing faults are constructed from bearing geometry and operating conditions. The class `BearingFrequencyBands` is a concrete subclass of `FaultFrequencyBands` that computes these bands. This construction yields structured representations of fault-related bands, including harmonic and sideband components together with their corresponding center and surround frequency ranges.

```

1  % Bearing frequency bands
2  bfb = BearingFrequencyBands( ...
3      bearingParams = bp, ...
4      sfrfsParams = sfrfsParams, ...
5      operatingConditions = oc);
6
7  % Compute bands
8  bfb.computeBands();
9
10 % Display bands table
11 disp(bfb.bandsTable);

```

FaultGroup	Description	Speed	Load	ReceptiveFieldBands
1	"Outer Race Fault"	35	12	1x10 cell
2	"Inner Race Fault"	35	12	1x50 cell
3	"Ball Fault"	35	12	1x50 cell
4	"Cage Fault"	35	12	1x10 cell
1	"Outer Race Fault"	37.5	11	1x10 cell
2	"Inner Race Fault"	37.5	11	1x50 cell
3	"Ball Fault"	37.5	11	1x50 cell
4	"Cage Fault"	37.5	11	1x10 cell
1	"Outer Race Fault"	40	10	1x10 cell
2	"Inner Race Fault"	40	10	1x50 cell
3	"Ball Fault"	40	10	1x50 cell
4	"Cage Fault"	40	10	1x10 cell

The number of bands varies across fault types due to the differential inclusion of sidebands.

10 Receptive Field Gain Functions (RFGFs)

Faults in rotating machinery, such as surface defects in bearings, excite the system quasi-periodically under constant-speed conditions. These excitations generate cyclostationary impulse trains that manifest along the harmonic family of the fault’s characteristic frequency. Receptive Field Gain Functions (RFGFs) consolidate these harmonic families into a single spectral mask that encodes the epistemic commitment to monitoring the induced harmonic lattice across fault types.

```

1 % Receptive field gain functions
2 rfgfs = ReceptiveFieldGainFunctions(bfb);
3
4 % Compute gain functions
5 rfgfs.computeGainFunctions(sp.getFrequencyDomain());
6
7 % Display gain functions table
8 disp(rfgfs.gainFunctionsTable);

```

FaultGroup	Description	Speed	Load	FrequencyBankMasks
1	"Outer Race Fault"	35	12	1x1 struct
2	"Inner Race Fault"	35	12	1x1 struct
3	"Ball Fault"	35	12	1x1 struct
4	"Cage Fault"	35	12	1x1 struct
1	"Outer Race Fault"	37.5	11	1x1 struct
2	"Inner Race Fault"	37.5	11	1x1 struct
3	"Ball Fault"	37.5	11	1x1 struct
4	"Cage Fault"	37.5	11	1x1 struct
1	"Outer Race Fault"	40	10	1x1 struct
2	"Inner Race Fault"	40	10	1x1 struct
3	"Ball Fault"	40	10	1x1 struct
4	"Cage Fault"	40	10	1x1 struct

10.1 Visualizing RFGFs

The `RFGFViewer` class provides a lightweight rendering layer on top of the `ReceptiveFieldGainFunctions` table representation.

```

1 % RFGF viewer
2 viewer = viz.RFGFViewer(rfgfs = rfgfs);
3 viewer.showLegend = true;
4
5 % Selection (operating condition)
6 sel = OperatingConditionSelection(speed = 35, load = 12);
7
8 % Fault type (outer race)
9 ft = SFRFsParametersRollingBearings. OUTER_RACE_FAULT_TYPE_NAME;
10
11 ax = viewer.render( ...
12     faultType = ft, ...
13     selection = sel, ...
14     frequencyLimits = [80 240], ...
15     titleText = "RFGFs (outer race, 35 Hz, 12 kN; [80, 240] Hz)");
16
17 grid(ax, "on");
18 xlabel(ax, "Frequency (Hz)");
19 ylabel(ax, "Gain");

```


10.2 Visualizing SFRFs Filtered Spectra

The `RunToFailureRFGFsFilteredSpectraViewer` is an embeddable visualization component for inspecting run-to-failure spectra after filtering with a selected RFGF mask (center, surround, or contrast). It renders the response matrix as a \log_{10} -scaled image over frequency and snapshot index. The following examples illustrate its use for analyzing degradation patterns in bearings.

10.2.1 Contrast Visualization

The following cell instantiates the viewer and configures it to display the contrast response for monitoring the first harmonic of outer-race faults. Since contrast is signed, the visualization selects either the positive or negative components according to the call parameters.

```

1  import structs.FrequencyBankMasksSchema
2
3  % Filtered spectra viewer
4  v = viz.RunToFailureRFGFsFilteredSpectraViewer( ...
5      memberTable = firstMember, ...
6      snapshotParameters = sp, ...
7      rfgfs = rfgfs);
8
9  % Selection (operating condition)
10 sel = OperatingConditionSelection(speed = 35, load = 12);
11
12 % Fault type (outer race)
13 ft = SFRFsParametersRollingBearings.OUTER_RACE_FAULT_TYPE_NAME;
14
15 % Contrast (signed log image)
16 % First harmonic (BPF0 = 107.9 Hz)
17 v.renderFiltered( ...
18     spectralColumn = FFTCols(1), ...
19     faultType = ft, ...
20     selection = sel, ...
21     maskType = FrequencyBankMasksSchema.CONTRAST, ...
22     freqRangeHz = [85 130], ...
23     titleText = "Positive contrast of absolute spectrum (BPF0 = 107.9 Hz, 85--130 Hz)", ...
24     invertGainSign = false);

```


The viewer enables inspection of bearing degradation through the positive contrast, noting that contrast may take both positive and negative values across the frequency domain. The following cell displays the negative contrast for the same parameters.

```

1  % Filtered spectra viewer
2  v = viz.RunToFailureRFGFsFilteredSpectraViewer( ...
3      memberTable = firstMember, ...
4      snapshotParameters = sp, ...
5      rfgfs = rfgfs);
6
7  % Selection (operating condition)
8  sel = OperatingConditionSelection(speed = 35, load = 12);
9
10 % Fault type (outer race)
11 ft = SFRFsParametersRollingBearings.OUTER_RACE_FAULT_TYPE_NAME;
12
13 % Contrast (signed log image)
14 % First harmonic (BPFO = 107.9 Hz)
15 v.renderFiltered( ...
16     spectralColumn = FFTCols(1), ...
17     faultType = ft, ...
18     selection = sel, ...
19     maskType = FrequencyBankMasksSchema.CONTRAST, ...
20     freqRangeHz = [85 130], ...
21     titleText = "Negative contrast of absolute spectrum (BPFO = 107.9 Hz, 85--130 Hz)", ...
22     invertGainSign = true);

```


The negative contrast for the selected SFRF parameters extends beyond the vicinity of BPFO = 107.9 Hz (outer race fault) into the nearby region corresponding to BPF1 = 102 Hz (inner race fault).

10.2.2 Visualizing Receptive Fields Components

The viewer enables visualization of the center and surround components prior to contrast computation. The following cell compares the centers of the first harmonic for BPFO and BPF1.

```

1  % Filtered spectra viewer
2  v = viz.RunToFailureRFGFsFilteredSpectraViewer( ...
3      memberTable = firstMember, ...
4      snapshotParameters = sp, ...
5      rfgfs = rfgfs);
6
7  % Selection (operating condition)
8  sel = OperatingConditionSelection(speed = 35, load = 12);
9
10 % Fault type (outer race)
11 ft = SFRFsParametersRollingBearings.OUTER_RACE_FAULT_TYPE_NAME;
12
13 % Center component (first harmonic, BPFO = 107.9 Hz)
14 v.renderFiltered( ...
15     spectralColumn = FFTCols(1), ...
16     faultType = ft, ...
17     selection = sel, ...
18     maskType = FrequencyBankMasksSchema.CENTER, ...
19     freqRangeHz = [85 130], ...
20     titleText = "Absolute spectrum filtered by center RFGF (BPFO = 107.9 Hz, 85--130 Hz)");

```



```

1  % Filtered spectra viewer
2  v = viz.RunToFailureRFGFsFilteredSpectraViewer( ...
3      memberTable = firstMember, ...
4      snapshotParameters = sp, ...
5      rfgfs = rfgfs);
6
7  % Selection (operating condition)
8  sel = OperatingConditionSelection(speed = 35, load = 12);
9
10 % Fault type (inner race)
11 ft = SFRFsParametersRollingBearings.INNER_RACE_FAULT_TYPE_NAME;
12
13 % Center component (first harmonic, BPFI = 102 Hz)
14 v.renderFiltered( ...
15     spectralColumn = FFTCols(1), ...
16     faultType = ft, ...
17     selection = sel, ...
18     maskType = FrequencyBankMasksSchema.CENTER, ...
19     freqRangeHz = [85 130], ...
20     titleText = "Absolute spectrum filtered by center RFGF (BPFI = 102 Hz, 85--130 Hz)");

```


The evolution of characteristic frequencies over time is distinctive. Despite the presence of an outer-race fault, elevated energy persists in the BPF band throughout the operational life, and its origin is not immediately evident. Interpretation of fault modes is further complicated by overlap of the monitoring bands. The following example considers the same parameters for visualization of the ball fault type.

```

1  % Filtered spectra viewer
2  v = viz.RunToFailureRFGFsFilteredSpectraViewer( ...
3      memberTable = firstMember, ...
4      snapshotParameters = sp, ...
5      rfgfs = rfgfs);
6
7  % Selection (operating condition)
8  sel = OperatingConditionSelection(speed = 35, load = 12);
9
10 % Fault type (ball)
11 ft = SFRFsParametersRollingBearings.BALL_FAULT_TYPE_NAME;
12
13 % Center component (first harmonic, BSF = 72.3 Hz)
14 v.renderFiltered( ...
15     spectralColumn = FFTCols(1), ...
16     faultType = ft, ...
17     selection = sel, ...
18     maskType = FrequencyBankMasksSchema.CENTER, ...
19     freqRangeHz = [65 140], ...
20     titleText = "Absolute spectrum filtered by center RFGF (BSF = 72.3 Hz, 65--140 Hz)");

```


Since two sidebands are considered, the second positive sideband $1F_b+2F_c$, corresponding to the first harmonic of BSF modulated by the second harmonic of FTF (cage), is centered at 99.3068 Hz and lies in close proximity to the first harmonic of BPF (102 Hz). This produces substantial overlap for the specified spectral masks while still exhibiting discernible footprints.

11 Spectral Fault Receptive Fields

Parallelized compute objects are available to characterize the full dataset. They are demonstrated in the Getting Started guide of the toolbox (see Section `SFRFsEnsembleProcessor` class). Here,

the focus is on parameterizations introduced in version 1.1.x, using agile computations and visualizations suited to exploring degradation trends.

11.1 Visualization of SFRFs

The `RunToFailureSFRFsViewer` is an embeddable visualization component for plotting scalar SFRF trajectories over snapshots in a run-to-failure ensemble member.

```
1  % SFRF viewer
2  sv = viz.RunToFailureSFRFsViewer( ...
3      memberTable = firstMember, ...
4      snapshotParameters = sp, ...
5      rfgfs = rfgfs);
6
7  % Selection (operating condition)
8  sel = OperatingConditionSelection(speed = 35, load = 12);
9
10 % Fault type (outer race)
11 ft = SFRFsParametersRollingBearings. OUTER_RACE_FAULT_TYPE_NAME;
12
13 sv.renderSFRF( ...
14     spectralColumn = FFTCols(1), ...
15     faultType = ft, ...
16     selection = sel, ...
17     titleText = "CI (outer race)");
```


12 Comparison of SFRFs to Standard Indicators

This section compares SFRFs with standard condition indicators computed from temporal snapshots and their spectra. The objective is to assess whether SFRFs provide trends that are not only informative but also more stable, tunable, and easier to interpret for degradation monitoring. All quantities are interpreted as trends derived from snapshot-wise responses, enabling direct comparison across descriptors.

12.1 SFRFs computation

```
1  %% Reference SFRF computation
2
3  % Signal and spectral column
4  signalField = "HorizontalAcceleration";
5  spectralColumn = FFTCols(1);
6
7  % Selection (operating condition)
8  sel = OperatingConditionSelection(speed = 35, load = 12);
9
10 % Fault type (outer race)
11 ft = SFRFsParametersRollingBearings. OUTER_RACE_FAULT_TYPE_NAME;
12
13 nSnapshots = size(firstMember, 1);
14
15 % Reference SFRF parameters
16 sharedParams = SFRFsParameters.buildSFRFsParameters( ...
17     'order', 0, ...
18     'numSidebands', 2, ...
19     'numHarmonics', 100, ...
20     'centerMask', SuperGaussianMaskParameters( ...
21         alpha = 2, ...
22         beta = 16), ...
23     'surroundMask', SuperGaussianMaskParameters( ...
24         alpha = 4, ...
25         beta = 1.7), ...
26     'inhibitionFactor', 0.9);
27
28 % Shared parameters (all fault types)
29 sfrfsParams = SFRFsParametersRollingBearings( ...
30     SameForAllFaultTypes = sharedParams);
31
32 % Bearing frequency bands
33 bfb = BearingFrequencyBands( ...
34     bearingParams = bp, ...
35     sfrfsParams = sfrfsParams, ...
36     operatingConditions = oc);
37
38 bfb.computeBands();
39
40 % Receptive field gain functions
41 rfgfs = ReceptiveFieldGainFunctions(bfb);
42 rfgfs.computeGainFunctions(sp.getFrequencyDomain());
43
44 % Center-surround computation
45 csc = CenterSurroundCompute( ...
46     snapshotParameters = sp, ...
47     rfgfs = rfgfs);
48
49 % Response function
50 rf = ReceptiveFieldResponseFunctions.integralAbs();
51
52 % Compute SFRF trend
53 sfrf = csc.compute( ...
54     memberTable = firstMember, ...
55     spectralColumn = spectralColumn, ...
56     faultType = ft, ...
57     selection = sel, ...
```

```

58     receptiveFieldResponseFunction = rf, ...
59     contrastMapping = function_handle.empty());
60
61     sfrfTrend = normalizeTrend(sfrf(:));
62
63     assert(numel(sfrfTrend) == nSnapshots, ...
64            'SFRF length mismatch with expected snapshot count.');
```

12.2 Time Domain Indicators

We now compute standard time-domain condition indicators from the temporal snapshots to establish a baseline for comparison with SFRFs. These descriptors are widely used in practice and provide a reference for assessing the stability, sensitivity, and interpretability of the trends obtained with SFRFs.

```

1  %% Time-domain descriptors vs SFRF
2
3  timeSignals = firstMember(signalField);
4  offset = 0.1;
5
6  timeLabels = [ ...
7     "SFRF"; ...
8     "RMS"; ...
9     "Peak-to-peak"; ...
10    "Crest factor"; ...
11    "Kurtosis"];
12
13  Ytime = zeros(nSnapshots, numel(timeLabels));
14  Ytime(:, 1) = sfrfTrend;
15
16  timeRMS = zeros(nSnapshots, 1);
17  timeP2P = zeros(nSnapshots, 1);
18  timeCF = zeros(nSnapshots, 1);
19  timeKurt = zeros(nSnapshots, 1);
20
21  for i = 1:nSnapshots
22      x = timeSignals{i};
23
24      timeRMS(i) = sqrt(mean(x.^2));
25      timeP2P(i) = max(x) - min(x);
26
27      xrms = timeRMS(i);
28      if xrms > 0
29          timeCF(i) = max(abs(x)) / xrms;
30      else
31          timeCF(i) = 0;
32      end
33
34      timeKurt(i) = kurtosis(x);
35  end
36
37  Ytime(:, 2) = normalizeTrend(timeRMS);
38  Ytime(:, 3) = normalizeTrend(timeP2P);
39  Ytime(:, 4) = normalizeTrend(timeCF);
40  Ytime(:, 5) = normalizeTrend(timeKurt);
41
42  plotStackedSFRFTrends( ...
43      Y = Ytime, ...
```

```

44 labels = timeLabels.', ...
45 offset = offset, ...
46 xlabel = "Snapshot index", ...
47 ylabel = "Normalized trend", ...
48 titleText = "Time-domain descriptors vs SFRF trend", ...
49 outputFile = "sfrf_vs_time_descriptors.pdf");

```


The comparison reveals that, for the selected parameterizations, SFRFs produce more stable and less noisy trends, while most standard time-domain indicators exhibit higher variability. Kurtosis is highly sensitive to severe faults, showing a pronounced spike around snapshot index 80, but provides limited insight into earlier degradation. Peak-to-peak captures degradation but with significant fluctuations. RMS remains relatively smooth and informative, although less sensitive to incipient changes.

As shown later in this study, a key advantage of SFRFs is their parameterizable sensitivity, enabling the construction of complementary perception channels without committing to a single descriptor behavior.

12.2.1 Comparison of SFRFs and Inverted RMS

```

1 plotSFRFvsInvertedRMS( ...
2   sfrfTrend = sfrfTrend, ...
3   rmsTrend = timeRMS, ...
4   xlabel = "Snapshot index", ...
5   ylabel = "Normalized aligned trend", ...
6   titleText = "Aligned comparison of SFRF and inverted RMS", ...
7   outputFile = "sfrf_vs_inverted_rms.pdf");

```


For the given parameterizations, SFRFs and RMS characterize the general degradation trend similarly prior to the severe fault, while SFRFs appear less smooth afterward. As shown in the following sections, alternative parameterizations can capture incipient faults that are not observable in these particular plots (see, for example, the Integral domain section).

12.3 Frequency Domain Indicators

We now compute standard frequency-domain condition indicators from the spectral representations of the snapshots. These descriptors are more directly comparable to SFRFs, as they operate on the same domain, and provide a reference for assessing how SFRFs relate to energy-based and spectral amplitude-based measures. Rather than competing with these descriptors, SFRFs can harness them within the same computational framework via RFRFs, with the added advantage of selectivity to different fault types and the ability to be parameterized to capture different aspects of degradation phenomena (see Section Custom RFRFs injection).

```

1  %% Frequency-domain descriptors vs SFRF
2
3  spectra = firstMember.(spectralColumn);
4  f = sp.getFrequencyDomain();
5
6  offset = 0.1;
7  epsEntropy = 1e-12;
8
9  freqLabels = [ ...
10     "SFRF"; ...
11     "Spectral energy"; ...
12     "Spectral RMS"; ...
13     "Peak spectral magnitude"; ...
14     "Spectral entropy"];
15
16  Yfreq = zeros(nSnapshots, numel(freqLabels));
17  Yfreq(:, 1) = sfrfTrend;
18
19  specEnergy = zeros(nSnapshots, 1);
20  specRMS = zeros(nSnapshots, 1);

```

```

21 specPeak = zeros(nSnapshots, 1);
22 specEntropy = zeros(nSnapshots, 1);
23
24 bandwidth = f(end) - f(1);
25
26 for i = 1:nSnapshots
27     X = spectra{i};
28     Xmag = abs(X(:));
29
30     specEnergy(i) = trapz(f, Xmag.^2);
31
32     if bandwidth > 0
33         specRMS(i) = sqrt(specEnergy(i) / bandwidth);
34     else
35         specRMS(i) = 0;
36     end
37
38     specPeak(i) = max(Xmag);
39
40     p = Xmag ./ (sum(Xmag) + epsEntropy);
41     specEntropy(i) = -sum(p .* log(p + epsEntropy));
42 end
43
44 Yfreq(:, 2) = normalizeTrend(specEnergy);
45 Yfreq(:, 3) = normalizeTrend(specRMS);
46 Yfreq(:, 4) = normalizeTrend(specPeak);
47 Yfreq(:, 5) = normalizeTrend(specEntropy);
48
49 plotStackedSFRFTrends( ...
50     Y = Yfreq, ...
51     labels = freqLabels.', ...
52     offset = offset, ...
53     xLabel = "Snapshot index", ...
54     yLabel = "Normalized trend", ...
55     titleText = "Frequency-domain descriptors vs SFRF trend", ...
56     outputFile = "sfrf_vs_frequency_descriptors.pdf");

```


As can be observed, this particular parameterization of SFRFs produces trends similar to spectral energy and spectral RMS, indicating that it captures global energy variations in the spectrum. Other parameterizations exhibit higher variability, reflecting increased sensitivity to localized spectral changes.

12.3.1 Comparison of SFRFs, and Inversion of Spectral Energy and Spectral RMS

For ease of comparison, the sign of the spectral energy and spectral RMS trends is reversed in the following plot to align their direction with that of the SFRFs.

```

1 plotSFRFvsReversedSpectralDescriptors( ...
2   sfrfTrend = sfrfTrend, ...
3   spectralEnergyTrend = specEnergy, ...
4   spectralRMSTrend = specRMS, ...
5   xlabel = "Snapshot index", ...
6   ylabel = "Normalized aligned trend", ...
7   titleText = ...
8     "Aligned comparison of SFRF, reversed spectral energy, and " + ...
9     "reversed spectral RMS", ...
10  outputFile = ...
11    "sfrf_vs_reversed_spectral_energy_rms.pdf");

```


13 Super-Gaussian Parameter Comparison

We now investigate how the shape and scale parameters of super-Gaussian masks influence the selectivity of SFRFs in the frequency domain. This is particularly relevant when fault-related components overlap or lie in close proximity, as the mask geometry determines the extent to which individual spectral contributions can be isolated or blended. In this section we demonstrate the effect of the shape parameter β in capturing degradation trends. The number of harmonics is kept constant to 10.

```

1  %% Compare SFRFs for different super-Gaussian betas (fixed N_h = 10)
2
3  % The shape parameter values to compare
4  % beta < 1 (non-convex)
5  % beta = 2 (Gaussian)
6  % beta >> 2 (box-like)
7  betas = [1/8, 1/4, 2, 8, 64];
8  Nh = 10;
9  nBetas = numel(betas);
10 nSnapshots = size(firstMember, 1);
11
12 % Receptive Field Response Function is the
13 % integral of absolute magnitude
14 rf = ReceptiveFieldResponseFunctions.integralAbs();
15
16 f = sp.getFrequencyDomain();
17
18 % Alpha set to half the previous bandwidths
19 alphaCenter = 4 / 2; % = 2
20 alphaSurround = 12 / 2; % = 6
21
22 % Compute and stack results
23 Y = zeros(nSnapshots, nBetas);
24 labels = strings(1, nBetas);
25
26 for i = 1:nBetas
27     beta = betas(i);
28
29     % Build SFRF parameterization with super-Gaussians
30     % For both center and surround
31     sharedParams = SFRFsParameters.buildSFRFsParameters( ...
32         'order', 0, ...
33         'numSidebands', 2, ...
34         'numHarmonics', Nh, ...
35         'centerMask', SuperGaussianMaskParameters( ...
36             alpha = alphaCenter, ...
37             beta = beta), ...
38         'surroundMask', SuperGaussianMaskParameters( ...
39             alpha = alphaSurround, ...
40             beta = beta), ...
41         'inhibitionFactor', 0.8647);
42
43     % Use the same SFRF parameters for all fault types
44     sfrfsParams = SFRFsParametersRollingBearings( ...
45         SameForAllFaultTypes = sharedParams);
46
47     % Compute frequency bands and gain functions
48     bfb = BearingFrequencyBands( ...
49         bearingParams = bp, ...
50         sfrfsParams = sfrfsParams, ...
51         operatingConditions = oc);
52
53     % Compute fault frequency bands
54     bfb.computeBands();
55
56     % Create RFGFs
57     rfgfs = ReceptiveFieldGainFunctions(bfb);
58     % Compute RFGFs
59     rfgfs.computeGainFunctions(f);

```

```

60
61 % Create center-surround compute object
62 csc = CenterSurroundCompute( ...
63     snapshotParameters = sp, ...
64     rfgfs = rfgfs);
65
66 % Compute SFRF trend
67 % We delegate computation to Center-Surround compute object
68 sfrf = csc.compute( ...
69     memberTable = firstMember, ...
70     spectralColumn = FFTCols(1), ...
71     faultType = ft, ...
72     selection = sel, ...
73     receptiveFieldResponseFunction = rf, ...
74     contrastMapping = function_handle.empty());
75
76 % Shape normalization
77 y = sfrf(:);
78 y = y - min(y);
79
80 ymax = max(y);
81 if ymax > 0
82     y = y ./ ymax;
83 end
84
85 assert(numel(y) == nSnapshots, ...
86     'SFRF length mismatch with expected snapshot count.');
87
88 % Stack results for later comparison
89 Y(:, i) = y;
90 labels(i) = "\beta=" + compose("%g", beta);
91 end
92
93 % Plot and export
94 % vertical offset for the plots
95 offset = 0.1;
96 plotStackedSFRFTrends( ...
97     Y = Y, ...
98     labels = labels, ...
99     offset = offset, ...
100     xlabel = "Snapshot index", ...
101     ylabel = "Outer race CI", ...
102     titleText = ...
103         "Normalized outer race CI degradation trends for " + ...
104         "Super-Gaussian profiles", ...
105     outputFile = "sfrf_vs_supergaussian_beta.pdf");

```


The shape parameter has a significant effect on sensitivity, particularly for $\beta < 1$. This must be interpreted with the understanding that non-convex masks reduce central dominance, thereby increasing sensitivity to background spectral content. This effect must also be considered in conjunction with the finite frequency resolution of the discrete spectrum. For non-convex masks, the effective contribution of the central frequency region may be under-sampled when the true frequency does not align with discrete frequency bins.

14 Harmonic Depth Comparison

We now investigate the effect of harmonic depth on the resulting SFRFs. The number of harmonics controls how much of the fault-induced spectral structure, i.e., the *harmonic lattice*, is incorporated into the response, directly influencing both the stability of the trends and their sensitivity to degradation. The number of considered harmonics is therefore an important parameter to set.

```

1  % Compare SFRFs for different harmonic depths (numHarmonics)
2
3  % Harmonic depths to compare
4  harmonicDepths = [1, 2, 3, 10, 100];
5  nDepths = numel(harmonicDepths);
6  nSnapshots = size(firstMember, 1);
7
8  % Operating condition of interest
9  sel = OperatingConditionSelection(speed=35, load=12);
10
11 % Fault type of interest
12 ft = SFRFsParametersRollingBearings.OUTER_RACE_FAULT_TYPE_NAME;
13
14 % Receptive Field Response Function is the
15 % integral of absolute magnitude
16 rf = ReceptiveFieldResponseFunctions.integralAbs();
17
18 f = sp.getFrequencyDomain();
19
20 % Compute and stack results

```

```

21 Y = zeros(nSnapshots, nDepths);
22 labels = strings(1, nDepths);
23
24 for i = 1:nDepths
25     H = harmonicDepths(i);
26
27     % Build SFRF parameterization with Gaussian masks
28     % for both center and surround
29     sharedParams = SFRFsParameters.buildSFRFsParameters( ...
30         'order', 0, ...
31         'numSidebands', 0, ...
32         'numHarmonics', H, ...
33         'centerMask', SuperGaussianMaskParameters( ...
34             alpha = 1, ...
35             beta = 4), ...
36         'surroundMask', SuperGaussianMaskParameters( ...
37             alpha = 2, ...
38             beta = 2), ...
39         'inhibitionFactor', 0.9);
40
41     % Use the same SFRF parameters for all fault types
42     sfrfsParams = SFRFsParametersRollingBearings( ...
43         SameForAllFaultTypes = sharedParams);
44
45     % Compute fault frequency bands
46     bfb = BearingFrequencyBands( ...
47         bearingParams = bp, ...
48         sfrfsParams = sfrfsParams, ...
49         operatingConditions = oc);
50
51     bfb.computeBands();
52
53     % Create and compute RFGFs
54     rfgfs = ReceptiveFieldGainFunctions(bfb);
55     rfgfs.computeGainFunctions(f);
56
57     % Create center-surround compute object
58     csc = CenterSurroundCompute( ...
59         snapshotParameters = sp, ...
60         rfgfs = rfgfs);
61
62     % Compute SFRF trend
63     sfrf = csc.compute( ...
64         memberTable = firstMember, ...
65         spectralColumn = FFTCols(1), ...
66         faultType = ft, ...
67         selection = sel, ...
68         receptiveFieldResponseFunction = rf, ...
69         contrastMapping = function_handle.empty());
70
71     % Shape normalization
72     y = sfrf(:);
73     y = y - min(y);
74
75     ymax = max(y);
76     if ymax > 0
77         y = y ./ ymax;
78     end
79

```

```

80     assert(numel(y) == nSnapshots, ...
81           'SFRF length mismatch with expected snapshot count. ');
82
83     % Stack results for later comparison
84     Y(:, i) = y;
85     labels(i) = "N_h=" + string(H);
86 end
87
88 % Plot and export
89 % Vertical offset for the plots
90 offset = 0.1;
91 plotStackedSFRFTrends( ...
92     Y = Y, ...
93     labels = labels, ...
94     offset = offset, ...
95     xlabel = "Snapshot index", ...
96     ylabel = "Outer race CI", ...
97     titleText = ...
98         "Outer race CI degradation trends varying number of harmonics", ...
99     outputFile = "sfrf_vs_harmonic_depth.pdf");

```


Using 100 harmonics provides consistent trends across parameter variations. For a low number of harmonics, however, the behavior of the SFRFs depends strongly on the scale and shape parameters of the super-Gaussian masks, as well as on the inhibition factor. Under this particular parameterization, a harmonic depth of 2 yields a response that is both sensitive and sufficiently smooth prior to the severe fault, clearly highlighting the onset of the incipient fault at snapshot index 66 (visually inferred from the sudden energy increase in the BPFO first harmonic; see Section Visualizing SFRFs Filtered Spectra). Nevertheless, by appropriate selection of these parameters, less sensitive and more stable trends can still be obtained even at low harmonic depths.

```

1 % Visualize the RF
2 % Create a viewer
3 viewer = viz.RFGFViewer(rfgfs = rfgfs);
4 viewer.showLegend = true;
5 ax = viewer.render( ...

```

```

6     faultType = ft, ...
7     selection = sel, ...
8     frequencyLimits = [80 140], ...
9     titleText = "RFGFs (outer race, 35 Hz, 12 kN; [80, 140] Hz band)";
10    grid(ax, "on");
11    xlabel(ax, "Frequency (Hz)");
12    ylabel(ax, "Gain");

```


RFGFs with a super-Gaussian center having $\beta = 4$ and a Gaussian surround ($\beta = 2$), as used in the example.

15 Receptive Field Response Functions (RFRFs)

We now explore how the choice of receptive field response function (RFRF) affects the resulting SFRFs. While previous sections focused on where information is extracted in the spectrum, RFRFs determine how this information is aggregated. Using the same SFRF parameterization as in the previous experiment, we introduce fractional integral orders to transform acceleration signals into quantities that exhibit velocity- and displacement-like scaling in the frequency domain, thereby enabling interpretations that extend beyond pure acceleration measurements.

15.1 Integral domain

```

1  %% Compare SFRF shapes for different integral orders p
2
3  % Integral orders to compare
4  orders = [0, 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2];
5  nOrders = numel(orders);
6  nSnapshots = size(firstMember, 1);
7
8  comments = [ ...
9      "(acceleration)"; ...
10     "(between acceleration and velocity)"; ...
11     "(velocity-like)"; ...
12     "(between velocity and displacement)"; ...
13     "(displacement-like)"];

```

```

14
15 labels = strings(1, nOrders);
16 for i = 1:nOrders
17     labels(i) = sprintf("p = %.1f %s", orders(i), comments(i));
18 end
19
20
21 % Standard shared params (fixed)
22 sharedParams = SFRFsParameters.buildSFRFsParameters( ...
23     'order', 0, ...
24     'numSidebands', 2, ...
25     'numHarmonics', 100, ...
26     'centerMask', SuperGaussianMaskParameters( ...
27         alpha = 1, ...
28         beta = 4), ...
29     'surroundMask', SuperGaussianMaskParameters( ...
30         alpha = 2, ...
31         beta = 2), ...
32     'inhibitionFactor', 0.9);
33
34 % Use the same SFRF parameters for all fault types
35 sfrfsParams = SFRFsParametersRollingBearings( ...
36     SameForAllFaultTypes = sharedParams);
37
38 % Compute fault frequency bands
39 bfb = BearingFrequencyBands( ...
40     bearingParams = bp, ...
41     sfrfsParams = sfrfsParams, ...
42     operatingConditions = oc);
43
44 bfb.computeBands();
45
46 % Create and compute RFGFs
47 rfgfs = ReceptiveFieldGainFunctions(bfb);
48 rfgfs.computeGainFunctions(sp.getFrequencyDomain());
49
50 % Create center-surround compute object
51 csc = CenterSurroundCompute( ...
52     snapshotParameters = sp, ...
53     rfgfs = rfgfs);
54
55
56 % Compute and stack results
57 Y = zeros(nSnapshots, nOrders);
58
59 for i = 1:nOrders
60     p = orders(i);
61
62     % Build receptive-field response function for order p
63     rf = ReceptiveFieldResponseFunctions.integralAbsFreqScaled( ...
64         order = p, ...
65         freqFloorHz = 1e-3);
66
67     % Compute SFRF trend
68     sfrf = csc.compute( ...
69         memberTable = firstMember, ...
70         spectralColumn = FFTCols(1), ...
71         faultType = ft, ...
72         selection = sel, ...

```

```

73     receptiveFieldResponseFunction = rf, ...
74     contrastMapping = function_handle.empty());
75
76     % Shape normalization
77     y = sfrf(:);
78     y = y - min(y);
79
80     ymax = max(y);
81     if ymax > 0
82         y = y ./ ymax;
83     end
84
85     assert(numel(y) == nSnapshots, ...
86         'SFRF length mismatch with expected snapshot count.');
```

87

```

88     % Stack results for later comparison
89     Y(:, i) = y;
90 end
91
92 % Plot and export
93 % Vertical offset for the plots
94 offset = 0.1;
95 plotStackedSFRFTrends( ...
96     Y = Y, ...
97     labels = labels, ...
98     offset = offset, ...
99     xlabel = "Snapshot index", ...
100    ylabel = "Normalized outer race CI", ...
101    titleText = ...
102    "Outer race CI degradation trends vs integral order p", ...
103    outputFile = "sfrf_vs_integral_order_p.pdf");
```


Variations in the integral order yield different sensitivities while preserving consistent degradation trends. In particular, velocity-like integrals exhibit stable behavior and remain sensitive to incipient faults.

15.2 Custom RFRFs Injection

We now demonstrate how custom receptive field response functions (RFRFs) can be injected to construct new *perception channels* tailored to specific analysis goals. This enables the incorporation of domain-specific descriptors, such as energy-based measures, within the SFRF framework while preserving its structural properties.

```
1  % Custom function: spectral energy RFRF
2  function r = energyRFRF(X, f)
3  % energyRFRF
4  % Computes the spectral energy over the masked frequency support.
5  %
6  %  $r(j) = \int |X(f,j)|^2 df$ 
7
8      r = trapz(f, abs(X).^2, 1);
9  end
10
11 function r = logMagnitudeRFRF(X, f)
12 % logMagnitudeRFRF
13 % Computes integrated log-magnitude over the masked spectral support.
14 %
15 %  $r(j) = \int \log_{10}(|X(f,j)| + \text{eps}) df$ 
16
17     epsVal = 1e-12; % avoid log(0)
18     r = trapz(f, log10(abs(X) + epsVal), 1);
19 end
20
21 % Custom RFRF injection
22 % Here we illustrate how to define and inject a custom RFRF by replacing
23 % the default magnitude integral with a spectral energy function.
24
25 % RFRFs to compare
26 rfrfNames = [ ...
27     "Magnitude integral"; ...
28     "Spectral energy"; ...
29     "Log-magnitude integral"];
30
31 nRFRFs = numel(rfrfNames);
32 nSnapshots = size(firstMember, 1);
33
34 % Operating condition of interest
35 sel = OperatingConditionSelection(speed = 35, load = 12);
36
37 % Fault type of interest
38 ft = SFRFsParametersRollingBearings. OUTER_RACE_FAULT_TYPE_NAME;
39
40
41 % Standard shared params (fixed)
42 sharedParams = SFRFsParameters.buildSFRFsParameters( ...
43     'order', 0, ...
44     'numSidebands', 2, ...
45     'numHarmonics', 100, ...
46     'centerMask', SuperGaussianMaskParameters( ...
47         alpha = 1, ...
48         beta = 4), ...
49     'surroundMask', SuperGaussianMaskParameters( ...
50         alpha = 2, ...
51         beta = 2), ...
52     'inhibitionFactor', 0.9);
```

```

53
54 sfrfsParams = SFRFsParametersRollingBearings( ...
55     SameForAllFaultTypes = sharedParams);
56
57 % Compute frequency bands and gain functions
58 bfb = BearingFrequencyBands( ...
59     bearingParams = bp, ...
60     sfrfsParams = sfrfsParams, ...
61     operatingConditions = oc);
62
63 bfb.computeBands();
64
65 rfgfs = ReceptiveFieldGainFunctions(bfb);
66 rfgfs.computeGainFunctions(sp.getFrequencyDomain());
67
68 csc = CenterSurroundCompute( ...
69     snapshotParameters = sp, ...
70     rfgfs = rfgfs);
71
72
73 % SFRFs default: integral of absolute magnitude
74 rfMagnitude = ReceptiveFieldResponseFunctions.integralAbs();
75 % Custom RFRF: energy
76 rfEnergy = @energyRFRF;
77 % Custom RFRF: log-magnitude
78 rfLogMag = @logMagnitudeRFRF;
79
80 rfrfs = {rfMagnitude, rfEnergy, rfLogMag};
81
82 % -----
83 % Compute and stack results
84 % -----
85 Y = zeros(nSnapshots, nRFRFs);
86
87 for i = 1:nRFRFs
88     rf = rfrfs{i};
89
90     sfrf = csc.compute( ...
91         memberTable = firstMember, ...
92         spectralColumn = FFTCols(1), ...
93         faultType = ft, ...
94         selection = sel, ...
95         receptiveFieldResponseFunction = rf, ...
96         contrastMapping = function_handle.empty());
97
98     % Shape normalization
99     y = sfrf(:);
100    y = y - min(y);
101
102    ymax = max(y);
103    if ymax > 0
104        y = y ./ ymax;
105    end
106
107    assert(numel(y) == nSnapshots, ...
108        'SFRF length mismatch with expected snapshot count.');
```

```

109
110    Y(:, i) = y;
111 end
```

```

112
113 % Plot and export
114 offset = 0.1;
115 plotStackedSFRFTrends( ...
116     Y = Y, ...
117     labels = rfrfNames.', ...
118     offset = offset, ...
119     xlabel = "Snapshot index", ...
120     ylabel = "Normalized outer race CI", ...
121     titleText = ...
122         "Outer race CI degradation trends for custom RFRF injection", ...
123     outputFile = "sfrf_vs_custom_rfrf_energy.pdf");

```


Spectral energy yields the most stable response, although at the cost of reduced sensitivity. By contrast, the logarithmic magnitude produces a more pronounced degradation trend than the default SFRF based on the integral of the spectrum magnitude.

15.3 Entropy and Contrast

We now investigate the interaction between entropy-based receptive field responses and different contrast mappings. While entropy captures the distributional structure of spectral energy, the choice of contrast mapping determines how differences between center and surround responses are emphasized, thereby influencing sensitivity to structural changes associated with degradation. This section showcases how different contrast mappings parameterize SFRFs and shape their resulting behavior.

```

1 %% Compare SFRF shapes for different contrast mappings (entropy response)
2
3 k = 1;
4
5 % Operating condition of interest
6 sel = OperatingConditionSelection(speed = 35, load = 12);
7
8 % Fault type of interest

```

```

9 ft = SFRFsParametersRollingBearings. OUTER_RACE_FAULT_TYPE_NAME;
10
11 maps = { ...
12     ContrastMappings.difference(k = k), ...
13     ContrastMappings.ratio(k = k, eps = 1e-12), ...
14     ContrastMappings.logRatio(k = k, eps = 1e-12), ...
15     ContrastMappings.normalizedDifference(k = k, eps = 1e-12)};
16
17 labels = [ ...
18     "Difference"; ...
19     "Ratio"; ...
20     "Log-ratio"; ...
21     "Normalized difference"];
22
23 nMaps = numel(maps);
24 nSnapshots = size(firstMember, 1);
25
26 % -----
27 % Shared SFRF parameters
28 % -----
29 sharedParams = SFRFsParameters.buildSFRFsParameters( ...
30     'order', 0, ...
31     'numSidebands', 2, ...
32     'numHarmonics', 7, ...
33     'centerMask', SuperGaussianMaskParameters( ...
34         alpha = 1, ...
35         beta = 4), ...
36     'surroundMask', SuperGaussianMaskParameters( ...
37         alpha = 2, ...
38         beta = 2), ...
39     'inhibitionFactor', 0.9);
40
41 % Use the same SFRF parameters for all fault types
42 sfrfsParams = SFRFsParametersRollingBearings( ...
43     SameForAllFaultTypes = sharedParams);
44
45 % Compute fault frequency bands
46 bfb = BearingFrequencyBands( ...
47     bearingParams = bp, ...
48     sfrfsParams = sfrfsParams, ...
49     operatingConditions = oc);
50
51 bfb.computeBands();
52
53 % Create and compute RGFs
54 rfgfs = ReceptiveFieldGainFunctions(bfb);
55 rfgfs.computeGainFunctions(sp.getFrequencyDomain());
56
57 % Create center-surround compute object
58 csc = CenterSurroundCompute( ...
59     snapshotParameters = sp, ...
60     rfgfs = rfgfs);
61
62 % Entropy RFRF
63 rf = ReceptiveFieldResponseFunctions.entropy( ...
64     normalize = false, ...
65     eps = 1e-12);
66
67 % Compute and stack results

```

```

68 Y = zeros(nSnapshots, nMaps);
69
70 for i = 1:nMaps
71     sfrf = csc.compute( ...
72         memberTable = firstMember, ...
73         spectralColumn = FFTCols(1), ...
74         faultType = ft, ...
75         selection = sel, ...
76         receptiveFieldResponseFunction = rf, ...
77         contrastMapping = maps{i});
78
79     y = sfrf(:);
80
81     assert(numel(y) == nSnapshots, ...
82         'SFRF length mismatch with expected snapshot count.');
```

```

83
84     Y(:, i) = y;
85 end
86
87 % Plot and export
88 plotSFRFTrends( ...
89     Y = Y, ...
90     labels = labels.', ...
91     xlabel = "Snapshot index", ...
92     ylabel = "Outer race CI (entropy response)", ...
93     titleText = ...
94     "Outer race CIs with entropy response vs contrast mappings", ...
95     legendLocation = "northeast", ...
96     outputFile = "sfrf_vs_contrast_mapping_entropy.pdf");
```


The entropy-based response exhibits higher variability, yet a discernible increase is observed during incipient degradation, followed by a decrease after severe failure. Sensitivity is higher for lower numbers of harmonics, reflecting both the influence of harmonic depth and the limitations of the current RFRF implementation.

16 SFRFsEnsembleProcessor benchmark

```
1 %% benchmark_xjtusy_sfrfs_decoupled_reps.m
2 % Full decoupling: copy ensemble per scenario, run, record, delete copy.
3 % No registry.
4 % FFT assumed precomputed in base ensemble files.
5 % 1 warm-up sweep + 10 recorded reps.
6 % Boxplots + median speedup/efficiency.
7
8 clear; clc;
9
10
11 % Configuration
12 maxWorkersToTry = 6;
13 numWarmupSweeps = 1;
14 numReps = 10;
15
16 temporalSnapshotColumns = { ...
17     "HorizontalAcceleration", "VerticalAcceleration"};
18
19 % Select base ensemble folder
20 dsBase = data.getXJTUSYEnsemble();
21 baseFolder = fileparts(dsBase.Files(1));
22
23 fprintf("Base ensemble folder:\n %s\n", baseFolder);
24
25     Base ensemble folder:
26     /home/stan/tmp/tocomputefft/select
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```

13     ballDiameter = 7.92, ...
14     pitchDiameter = 34.55, ...
15     contactAngle = 0);
16
17     sfrfsParams = SFRFsParameters.createSFRFsParameters( ...
18         order = 0, ...
19         numHarmonics = 10, ...
20         numSidebands = 2, ...
21         sigmaCenter = [4, 2], ...
22         sigmaSurround = [12, 2], ...
23         inhibitionFactor = 1/3);
24
25     sbp = SFRFsParametersRollingBearings(SameForAllFaultTypes = sfrfsParams);
26
27     bearingFrequencyBands = BearingFrequencyBands( ...
28         bearingParams = bp, ...
29         sfrfsParams = sbp, ...
30         operatingConditions = oc);
31
32     % Results storage
33     runId = string(datetime("now", "Format", "yyyyMMdd_HH:mm:ss"));
34     resultsFile = "bench_sfrfs_decoupled_" + runId + ".mat";
35
36     nW = numel(workerCounts);
37     nRows = numReps * nW;
38
39     Rep = zeros(nRows, 1);
40     NumWorkers = zeros(nRows, 1);
41     Seconds = nan(nRows, 1);
42     Status = strings(nRows, 1);
43     Message = strings(nRows, 1);
44
45     Results = table(Rep, NumWorkers, Seconds, Status, Message);
46
47     rowPtr = 0;
48
49
50     % Root temp folder for copies
51     rootTmp = fullfile(tempdir, "sfrfs_bench_" + runId);
52     if ~exist(rootTmp, 'dir')
53         mkdir(rootTmp);
54     end
55
56     % Sweeps
57     totalSweeps = numWarmupSweeps + numReps;
58
59     for sweep = 1:totalSweeps
60         isWarmup = sweep <= numWarmupSweeps;
61
62         if isWarmup
63             fprintf("\nWarm-up sweep %d/%d (not recorded)\n", ...
64                 sweep, numWarmupSweeps);
65             rep = 0;
66             repTag = "warmup" + sweep;
67         else
68             rep = sweep - numWarmupSweeps;
69             repTag = "rep" + rep;
70             fprintf("\nRecorded sweep %d/%d\n", rep, numReps);
71         end

```

```

72
73 for wi = 1:nW
74     kW = workerCounts(wi);
75     tag = repTag + "_w" + kW;
76
77     fprintf(" Workers=%d (%s) ... ", kW, tag);
78
79     % Create isolated working copy (NOT timed)
80     workFolder = fullfile(rootTmp, tag);
81     if exist(workFolder, 'dir')
82         rmdir(workFolder, 's');
83     end
84     mkdir(workFolder);
85     copyfile(baseFolder, workFolder);
86
87     try
88         % New datastore handle pointing to the isolated copy
89         ds = data.getXJTUSYEnsemble(workFolder);
90
91         % Ensure FFT cols are visible (handle-level only)
92         broker0 = EnsembleBroker( ...
93             ensembleObject = ds, ...
94             getFilesFunction = @(obj) obj.Files, ...
95             temporalSnapshotColumns = cellstr( ...
96                 temporalSnapshotColumns));
97
98         FFTCols = string(cellfun( ...
99             @(c0) broker0.mapToSpectralColumn(c0), ...
100             cellstr(temporalSnapshotColumns), ...
101             'UniformOutput', false)).';
102
103         ds.DataVariables = unique([ds.DataVariables(:); FFTCols(:)], ...
104             "stable");
105         ds.SelectedVariables = unique([ds.SelectedVariables(:); ...
106             FFTCols(:)], "stable");
107         reset(ds);
108
109         % SFRFs broker
110         broker = SFRFsEnsembleBroker( ...
111             EnsembleObject = ds, ...
112             GetFilesFunction = @(obj) obj.Files, ...
113             TemporalSnapshotColumns = cellstr( ...
114                 temporalSnapshotColumns));
115
116         % Warm pool (NOT timed)
117         localWarmPool(kW);
118
119         % Timed compute
120         processor = SFRFsEnsembleProcessor( ...
121             numWorkers = kW, ...
122             ensemble = broker, ...
123             frequencyBands = bearingFrequencyBands, ...
124             snapshotParameters = sp);
125
126         tic;
127         processor.process();
128         tSec = toc;
129
130         fprintf("ok (%.2fs)\n", tSec);

```

```

131
132     if ~isWarmup
133         rowPtr = rowPtr + 1;
134         Results.Rep(rowPtr) = rep;
135         Results.NumWorkers(rowPtr) = kW;
136         Results.Seconds(rowPtr) = tSec;
137         Results.Status(rowPtr) = "ok";
138         Results.Message(rowPtr) = "";
139     end
140
141     catch ME
142         fprintf("FAILED\n");
143
144         if ~isWarmup
145             rowPtr = rowPtr + 1;
146             Results.Rep(rowPtr) = rep;
147             Results.NumWorkers(rowPtr) = kW;
148             Results.Seconds(rowPtr) = NaN;
149             Results.Status(rowPtr) = "failed";
150             Results.Message(rowPtr) = string(ME.identifier) + ...
151                 " | " + string(ME.message);
152         end
153     end
154
155     % Delete isolated copy to keep disk under control
156     if exist(workFolder, 'dir')
157         rmdir(workFolder, 's');
158     end
159
160     % Save after each recorded scenario
161     if ~isWarmup
162         save(resultsFile, ...
163             'Results', 'runId', 'workerCounts', 'numReps', ...
164             'numWarmupSweeps', 'maxWorkersToTry', 'capW');
165     end
166 end
167 end

```

```

Warm-up sweep 1/1 (not recorded)
Workers=1 (warmup1_w1) ...
Starting parallel pool (parpool) using the 'Processes' profile ...
Connected to parallel pool with 1 workers.
ok (567.45s)
Workers=2 (warmup1_w2) ...
Parallel pool using the 'Processes' profile is shutting down.
Starting parallel pool (parpool) using the 'Processes' profile ...
Connected to parallel pool with 2 workers.
ok (347.39s)
Workers=3 (warmup1_w3) ...
Parallel pool using the 'Processes' profile is shutting down.
Starting parallel pool (parpool) using the 'Processes' profile ...
Connected to parallel pool with 3 workers.
ok (244.59s)
Workers=4 (warmup1_w4) ...
Parallel pool using the 'Processes' profile is shutting down.
Starting parallel pool (parpool) using the 'Processes' profile ...
Connected to parallel pool with 4 workers.
ok (218.28s)
Workers=5 (warmup1_w5) ...
Parallel pool using the 'Processes' profile is shutting down.
Starting parallel pool (parpool) using the 'Processes' profile ...
Connected to parallel pool with 5 workers.
ok (218.44s)
Workers=6 (warmup1_w6) ...
Parallel pool using the 'Processes' profile is shutting down.
Starting parallel pool (parpool) using the 'Processes' profile ...
Connected to parallel pool with 6 workers.
ok (214.30s)
Recorded sweep 1/10
Workers=1 (repi_w1) ...

```



```

ok (215.35s)
Recorded sweep 10/10
  Workers=1 (rep10_w1) ...
Parallel pool using the 'Processes' profile is shutting down.
Starting parallel pool (parpool) using the 'Processes' profile ...
Connected to parallel pool with 1 workers.
ok (592.23s)
  Workers=2 (rep10_w2) ...
Parallel pool using the 'Processes' profile is shutting down.
Starting parallel pool (parpool) using the 'Processes' profile ...
Connected to parallel pool with 2 workers.
ok (349.43s)
  Workers=3 (rep10_w3) ...
Parallel pool using the 'Processes' profile is shutting down.
Starting parallel pool (parpool) using the 'Processes' profile ...
Connected to parallel pool with 3 workers.
ok (246.34s)
  Workers=4 (rep10_w4) ...
Parallel pool using the 'Processes' profile is shutting down.
Starting parallel pool (parpool) using the 'Processes' profile ...
Connected to parallel pool with 4 workers.
ok (217.35s)
  Workers=5 (rep10_w5) ...
Parallel pool using the 'Processes' profile is shutting down.
Starting parallel pool (parpool) using the 'Processes' profile ...
Connected to parallel pool with 5 workers.
ok (212.72s)
  Workers=6 (rep10_w6) ...
Parallel pool using the 'Processes' profile is shutting down.
Starting parallel pool (parpool) using the 'Processes' profile ...
Connected to parallel pool with 6 workers.
ok (211.73s)

```

```

1
2 Results = Results(1:rowPtr, :);
3
4 % Cleanup root temp folder (should be empty, but remove anyway)
5 if exist(rootTmp, 'dir')
6     rmdir(rootTmp, 's');
7 end
8
9 % Boxplot of runtimes
10 okRows = Results.Status == "ok" & ~isnan(Results.Seconds);
11 Rok = Results(okRows, :);
12
13 if isempty(Rok)
14     warning("No successful runs to plot.");
15     return;
16 end
17
18 figure('Name', 'SFRFs runtime boxplot');
19 boxplot(Rok.Seconds, Rok.NumWorkers);
20 grid on;
21 xlabel('Num workers');
22 ylabel('Seconds');
23 title(sprintf("SFRFs runtime (10 reps, warm-up=%d sweep)", ...
24     numWarmupSweeps));

```



```

1
2 % Median runtime, speedup, efficiency
3 nW = numel(workerCounts);
4 medTime = nan(nW, 1);
5
6 for wi = 1:nW
7     kW = workerCounts(wi);
8     x = Rok.Seconds(Rok.NumWorkers == kW);
9     medTime(wi) = median(x);
10 end
11
12 t1 = medTime(workerCounts == 1);
13 speedupMed = t1 ./ medTime;
14 effMed = speedupMed ./ workerCounts;
15
16 figure('Name', 'Median runtime vs workers');
17 plot(workerCounts, medTime, '-o');
18 grid on;
19 xlabel('Num workers');
20 ylabel('Median seconds');
21 title('Median SFRFs runtime vs workers');

```



```

1
2 figure('Name', 'Median speedup vs workers');
3 plot(workerCounts, speedupMed, '-o');
4 grid on;
5 xlabel('Num workers');
6 ylabel('Median speedup (T1 / Tn)');
7 title('Median speedup vs workers');

```



```

1
2 figure('Name', 'Median efficiency vs workers');
3 plot(workerCounts, effMed, '-o');
4 grid on;
5 xlabel('Num workers');
6 ylabel('Median efficiency (speedup / n)');
7 title('Median efficiency vs workers');

```



```

1
2 save(resultsFile, ...
3     'Results', 'runId', 'workerCounts', 'numReps', 'numWarmupSweeps', ...
4     'medTime', 'speedupMed', 'effMed');
5
6 fprintf("\nDone. Results saved to: %s\n", resultsFile);

```

Done. Results saved to: bench_sfrfs_decoupled_20260115_195345.mat

The observed stagnation in performance is attributable to significant differences in file sizes across the different bearings.

17 Concluding Remarks

This study showcases the new parameterizations introduced in the SFRFs MATLAB toolbox [2], available from version 1.1.x. The toolbox significantly extends previous functionality by enabling the injection of custom Receptive Field Response Functions (RFRFs). As demonstrated in the computational notebook, SFRF-based condition indicators do not replace standard descriptors, but rather provide a structured framework to incorporate and control them, enabling different aspects of degradation to be emphasized through parameterization. Our comparison against classical temporal- and frequency-based condition indicators suggests that SFRFs can provide more informative degradation trends, in the sense that, unlike traditional descriptors, they selectively attend to harmonic families associated with specific fault types. There is a clear trade-off between the smoothness of the condition indicators and their sensitivity to capture incipient faults. For instance, raw RMS is informative of the general trend but fails to detect incipient faults, whereas certain parameterizations of SFRFs can capture such events. It is also apparent that further investigation is required to build accurate accounts of degradation that reliably distinguish aleatoric uncertainty from consistent incipient fault events. In this context, variability and its trend should not be regarded as noise per se.

In our positioning paper [1], we demonstrated that SFRFs can be optimized from data using a multi-objective genetic algorithm. A tailored, hybrid combinatorial multi-objective optimization module is currently under development. At the same time, we adhere to the well-known principle that premature optimization is the root of all evil, and therefore emphasize the importance of properly

defined optimization criteria. For instance, we have shown that smoothness and monotonicity alone may fail to capture incipient faults.

Inspired by the biology of vision, our approach adopts the concept of complementary and parallel perception channels. It is unlikely that a single descriptor can simultaneously satisfy competing objectives such as smoothness, sensitivity, and interpretability. The SFRF framework enables the construction of multiple complementary channels to address these trade-offs. Complementarity should be interpreted along two dimensions: first, as the concurrent monitoring of different aspects and fault types; and second, as channels switching on and off as the degradation stage evolves along the degradation trajectory. The visual system provides an analogous mechanism, for example transitioning from rod photoreceptors in dim light (scotopic vision), which are sensitive enough to respond reliably to a handful of photons, to mesopic conditions where cones begin to operate, and finally to photopic vision, where rods are no longer responsive and cones alone handle visual perception. This arrangement allows the retina to cover a dynamic range of approximately 11 orders of magnitude in luminance.

The analysis also highlights that fault characterization benefits more from increased frequency resolution than from higher temporal resolution. In practice, this can be achieved by extending the duration of temporal snapshots rather than increasing the sampling frequency.

The toolbox has been carefully designed and tested, with particular attention to observability via logging and performance via parallelization. While these aspects are not central to the conceptual contributions, they are essential for deployment in practical PHM pipelines. This is complemented by a shift toward a more functional design based on behavior injection, enabling more agile, research-oriented workflows, such as the exploration of degradation phenomena from vibration signals.

MATLAB support for real-time and embedded deployment is well established through toolchains such as MATLAB Coder and Simulink Real-Time, which enable code generation and integration into production environments. While the present work focuses on research-oriented development and analysis, the proposed framework remains compatible with such deployment workflows.

In this setting, the framework enables the selective, fault-oriented harnessing of spectral descriptors through parameterized receptive fields, allowing different aspects of degradation to be emphasized in a controlled manner.

18 Auxiliary Functions

18.1 Benchmark Helper

```
1 % Sanity run before timing
2 function localWarmPool(kW)
3 % Ensure a Processes pool with kW workers is running. kW==1 -> no pool.
4     if kW <= 1
5         return;
6     end
7
8     p = gcp('nocreate');
9     if isempty(p) || p.NumWorkers ~= kW || ~strcmp(p.Cluster.Profile, ...
10         'Processes')
11         if ~isempty(p)
12             delete(p);
13         end
14         parpool('Processes', kW);
15     end
16 end
```

18.2 Normalization Helper

```
1 function y = normalizeTrend(x)
2 % normalizeTrend
3 % Shift to zero minimum and scale to unit maximum if possible.
4
5     y = x(:);
6     y = y - min(y);
7
8     ymax = max(y);
9     if ymax > 0
10         y = y ./ ymax;
11     end
12 end
```

18.3 SFRFs vs RMS Plot

```
1 function fig = plotSFRFvsInvertedRMS(args)
2 % plotSFRFvsInvertedRMS
3 % Plot an aligned comparison between the SFRF trend and inverted RMS.
4
5 arguments
6     args.sfrfTrend (:,1) double
7     args.rmsTrend (:,1) double
8     args.xLabel (1,1) string = "Snapshot index"
9     args.yLabel (1,1) string = "Normalized aligned trend"
10    args.titleText (1,1) string = ...
11        "Aligned comparison of SFRF and inverted RMS"
12    args.outputFile (1,1) string = "sfrf_vs_inverted_rms.pdf"
13 end
14
15 sfrfTrend = args.sfrfTrend(:);
16 rmsTrend = args.rmsTrend(:);
17
18 assert(numel(rmsTrend) == numel(sfrfTrend), ...
19     'rmsTrend and sfrfTrend must have the same length.');
```

```
20
21 sfrfAligned = normalizeTrend(sfrfTrend);
22 rmsAligned = normalizeTrend(-rmsTrend);
23
24
25 % Geometry: plotting area = 8x5 inches
26 plotW = 8;
27 plotH = 5;
28
29 left = 0.7;
30 right = 0.3;
31 bottom = 0.7;
32 top = 0.6;
33
34 figW = plotW + left + right;
35 figH = plotH + bottom + top;
36
37 axPos = [ ...
38     left/figW, ...
39     bottom/figH, ...
40     plotW/figW, ...
```

```

41     plotH/figH];
42
43 fig = figure( ...
44     'Units', 'inches', ...
45     'Position', [1 1 figW figH], ...
46     'PaperUnits', 'inches', ...
47     'PaperPosition', [0 0 figW figH], ...
48     'PaperSize', [figW figH], ...
49     'PaperPositionMode', 'manual');
50
51 ax = axes( ...
52     'Parent', fig, ...
53     'Units', 'normalized', ...
54     'Position', axPos, ...
55     'Box', 'on');
56
57 ax.ActivePositionProperty = 'position';
58 ax.PositionConstraint = 'innerposition';
59 ax.PositionMode = 'manual';
60
61 hold(ax, 'on');
62 grid(ax, 'on');
63
64 plot(ax, sfrfAligned, ...
65     'LineStyle', '-', ...
66     'LineWidth', 1.4, ...
67     'DisplayName', "SFRF");
68
69 plot(ax, rmsAligned, ...
70     'LineStyle', '-', ...
71     'LineWidth', 1.4, ...
72     'DisplayName', "Inverted RMS");
73
74 ax.LineWidth = 0.75;
75 ax.BoxStyle = "full";
76 set(ax, 'FontSize', 9);
77
78 xlabel(ax, args.xLabel);
79 ylabel(ax, args.yLabel);
80 title(ax, args.titleText, 'Interpreter', 'none');
81
82 t = ax.Title;
83 set(t, 'FontSize', 10, 'FontWeight', 'normal');
84
85 lgd = legend(ax, 'Location', 'best');
86 lgd.Box = 'off';
87 lgd.Interpreter = 'none';
88
89 hold(ax, 'off');
90
91 exportgraphics(fig, args.outputFile, ...
92     'ContentType', 'vector', ...
93     'Resolution', 300);
94 end

```

18.4 SFRFs vs Spectral CIs

```

1 function fig = plotSFRFvsReversedSpectralDescriptors(args)
2 % plotSFRFvsReversedSpectralDescriptors
3 % Plot an aligned comparison between the SFRF trend and the reversed
4 % spectral energy and spectral RMS trends.
5
6 arguments
7     args.sfrfTrend(:,1) double
8     args.spectralEnergyTrend(:,1) double
9     args.spectralRMSTrend(:,1) double
10    args.xLabel(1,1) string = "Snapshot index"
11    args.yLabel(1,1) string = "Normalized aligned trend"
12    args.titleText(1,1) string = ...
13        "Aligned comparison of SFRF and reversed spectral descriptors"
14    args.outputFile(1,1) string = ...
15        "sfrf_vs_reversed_spectral_energy_rms.pdf"
16 end
17
18 sfrfTrend = args.sfrfTrend(:);
19 spectralEnergyTrend = args.spectralEnergyTrend(:);
20 spectralRMSTrend = args.spectralRMSTrend(:);
21
22 n = numel(sfrfTrend);
23
24 assert(numel(spectralEnergyTrend) == n, ...
25     'spectralEnergyTrend and sfrfTrend must have the same length. ');
26 assert(numel(spectralRMSTrend) == n, ...
27     'spectralRMSTrend and sfrfTrend must have the same length. ');
28
29 sfrfAligned = normalizeTrend(sfrfTrend);
30 spectralEnergyAligned = normalizeTrend(-spectralEnergyTrend);
31 spectralRMSAligned = normalizeTrend(-spectralRMSTrend);
32
33 % Geometry: plotting area = 8x5 inches
34 plotW = 8;
35 plotH = 5;
36
37 left = 0.7;
38 right = 0.3;
39 bottom = 0.7;
40 top = 0.6;
41
42 figW = plotW + left + right;
43 figH = plotH + bottom + top;
44
45 axPos = [ ...
46     left/figW, ...
47     bottom/figH, ...
48     plotW/figW, ...
49     plotH/figH];
50
51 fig = figure( ...
52     'Units', 'inches', ...
53     'Position', [1 1 figW figH], ...
54     'PaperUnits', 'inches', ...
55     'PaperPosition', [0 0 figW figH], ...
56     'PaperSize', [figW figH], ...
57     'PaperPositionMode', 'manual');
58
59 ax = axes( ...

```

```

60     'Parent', fig, ...
61     'Units', 'normalized', ...
62     'Position', axPos, ...
63     'Box', 'on');
64
65     ax.ActivePositionProperty = 'position';
66     ax.PositionConstraint = 'innerposition';
67     ax.PositionMode = 'manual';
68
69     hold(ax, 'on');
70     grid(ax, 'on');
71
72     plot(ax, sfrfAligned, ...
73         'LineStyle', '-', ...
74         'LineWidth', 1.4, ...
75         'DisplayName', "SFRF");
76
77     plot(ax, spectralEnergyAligned, ...
78         'LineStyle', '-', ...
79         'LineWidth', 1.4, ...
80         'DisplayName', "Reversed spectral energy");
81
82     plot(ax, spectralRMSAligned, ...
83         'LineStyle', '-', ...
84         'LineWidth', 1.6, ...
85         'DisplayName', "Reversed spectral RMS");
86
87     ax.LineWidth = 0.75;
88     ax.BoxStyle = "full";
89     set(ax, 'FontSize', 9);
90
91     xlabel(ax, args.xLabel);
92     ylabel(ax, args.yLabel);
93     title(ax, args.titleText, 'Interpreter', 'none');
94
95     t = ax.Title;
96     set(t, 'FontSize', 10, 'FontWeight', 'normal');
97
98     lgd = legend(ax, 'Location', 'best');
99     lgd.Box = 'off';
100    lgd.Interpreter = 'none';
101
102    hold(ax, 'off');
103
104    exportgraphics(fig, args.outputFile, ...
105        'ContentType', 'vector', ...
106        'Resolution', 300);
107 end

```

18.5 SFRFs Trends Plots

```

1 function fig = plotSFRFTrends(args)
2 % plotSFRFTrends
3 % Plot raw SFRF trends and export the figure.
4
5 arguments
6     args.Y (:,:) double
7     args.labels (1,:) string

```

```

8     args.xLabel (1,1) string = "Snapshot index"
9     args.yLabel (1,1) string = "Response"
10    args.titleText (1,1) string = "SFRF comparison"
11    args.legendLocation (1,1) string = "best"
12    args.outputFile (1,1) string = "sfrf_comparison.pdf"
13    end
14
15    Y = args.Y;
16    labels = args.labels;
17
18
19    % Geometry: plotting area = 8x5 inches (DATA AREA)
20    plotW = 8;
21    plotH = 5;
22
23    left = 0.7;
24    right = 0.3;
25    bottom = 0.7;
26    top = 0.6;
27
28    figW = plotW + left + right;
29    figH = plotH + bottom + top;
30
31    axPos = [ ...
32        left / figW, ...
33        bottom / figH, ...
34        plotW / figW, ...
35        plotH / figH];
36
37    fig = figure( ...
38        'Units', 'inches', ...
39        'Position', [1 1 figW figH], ...
40        'PaperUnits', 'inches', ...
41        'PaperPosition', [0 0 figW figH], ...
42        'PaperSize', [figW figH], ...
43        'PaperPositionMode', 'manual');
44
45    ax = axes( ...
46        'Parent', fig, ...
47        'Units', 'normalized', ...
48        'Position', axPos, ...
49        'Box', 'on');
50
51    % Lock axes geometry
52    ax.ActivePositionProperty = 'position';
53    ax.PositionConstraint = 'innerposition';
54    ax.PositionMode = 'manual';
55
56    hold(ax, 'on');
57    grid(ax, 'on');
58
59    markers = {'o', 's', 'd', '^', 'v'};
60    markerEvery = 25;
61
62    nCurves = size(Y, 2);
63
64    for i = 1:nCurves
65        y = Y(:, i);
66

```

```

67     markerStart = 1 + round((i-1) * markerEvery / nCurves);
68     markerIdx = markerStart:markerEvery:numel(y);
69
70     plot(ax, y, ...
71         'LineStyle', '-', ...
72         'LineWidth', 1.2, ...
73         'Marker', markers{mod(i-1, numel(markers)) + 1}, ...
74         'MarkerIndices', markerIdx, ...
75         'DisplayName', labels(i));
76 end
77
78 set(ax, 'FontSize', 9);
79 xlabel(ax, args.xLabel);
80 ylabel(ax, args.yLabel);
81
82 title(ax, args.titleText, 'Interpreter', 'none');
83 t = ax.Title;
84 set(t, 'FontSize', 10, 'FontWeight', 'normal');
85
86 box(ax, 'on');
87 ax.LineWidth = 0.75;
88
89 lgd = legend(ax, 'Location', char(args.legendLocation));
90 lgd.Box = 'off';
91 lgd.Interpreter = 'none';
92
93 ax.Position = axPos;
94
95 hold(ax, 'off');
96
97 exportgraphics(fig, args.outputFile, ...
98     'ContentType', 'vector', ...
99     'Resolution', 300);
100 end

```

18.6 SFRFs Stacked Plot

```

1 function fig = plotStackedSFRFTrends(args)
2 % plotStackedSFRFTrends
3 % Plot vertically offset normalized trends and export the figure.
4
5 arguments
6     args.Y (:,:) double
7     args.labels (1,:) string
8     args.offset (1,1) double = 0.1
9     args.xLabel (1,1) string = "Snapshot index"
10    args.yLabel (1,1) string = "Response"
11    args.titleText (1,1) string = "SFRF comparison"
12    args.outputFile (1,1) string = "sfrf_comparison.pdf"
13 end
14
15 Y = args.Y;
16 labels = args.labels;
17 offset = args.offset;
18
19 % Geometry: plotting area = 8x5 inches (DATA AREA)
20 plotW = 8; % inches
21 plotH = 5; % inches

```

```

22
23 left = 0.7;
24 right = 0.3;
25 bottom = 0.7;
26 top = 0.6;
27
28 figW = plotW + left + right;
29 figH = plotH + bottom + top;
30
31 axPos = [ ...
32     left/figW, ...
33     bottom/figH, ...
34     plotW/figW, ...
35     plotH/figH];
36
37 fig = figure( ...
38     'Units','inches', ...
39     'Position',[1 1 figW figH], ...
40     'PaperUnits','inches', ...
41     'PaperPosition',[0 0 figW figH], ...
42     'PaperSize',[figW figH], ...
43     'PaperPositionMode','manual');
44
45 ax = axes( ...
46     'Parent',fig, ...
47     'Units','normalized', ...
48     'Position',axPos, ...
49     'Box','on');
50
51 % Lock axes geometry
52 ax.ActivePositionProperty = 'position';
53 ax.PositionConstraint = 'innerposition';
54 ax.PositionMode = 'manual';
55
56 hold(ax,'on');
57 grid(ax,'on');
58
59 lineStyle = '-';
60 markers = {'o','s','d','^','v'};
61 markerEvery = 25;
62
63 nCurves = size(Y, 2);
64
65 for i = 1:nCurves
66     y = Y(:, i) + (i-1) * offset;
67     mk = markers{mod(i-1, numel(markers)) + 1};
68
69     plot(ax, y, ...
70         'LineStyle', lineStyle, ...
71         'LineWidth', 1.2, ...
72         'Marker', mk, ...
73         'MarkerIndices', 1:markerEvery:numel(y), ...
74         'DisplayName', labels(i));
75 end
76
77 % Styling
78 yticks(ax, []);
79 ax.YGrid = "off";
80 ax.LineWidth = 0.75;

```

```

81     ax.BoxStyle = "full";
82     set(ax, 'FontSize', 9);
83
84     xlabel(ax, args.xLabel);
85     ylabel(ax, args.yLabel + ...
86           " (vertical offset = " + string(offset) + ")");
87     title(ax, args.titleText, "Interpreter", "none");
88
89     t = ax.Title;
90     set(t, 'FontSize', 10, 'FontWeight', 'normal');
91
92     lgd = legend(ax, 'Location', 'southwest');
93     lgd.Box = 'off';
94
95     hold(ax, 'off');
96
97     % Export
98     exportgraphics(fig, args.outputFile, ...
99                   'ContentType', 'vector', ...
100                  'Resolution', 300);
101 end

```

19 Acknowledgments

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